

A sophisticated model for rating water quality

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HIGHLIGHTS

- The IEWQI model is a reliable method for determining the accuracy, reliability, and affordability of transitional and coastal water quality.
- Model could be efficient for optimizing model eclipsing and ambiguity problems in order to reduce model uncertainty
- The uncertainty in the IEWQI model is <2 %.
- The results of model evaluation metrics NSE and MEF reveal that the model could be ranked more accurately for water quality at each monitoring site.
- Based on the findings, the performance of IEWQI applications reveals that suggested indicators might be adequate and reliable to monitor water.

GRAPHICAL ABSTRACT

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ABSTRACT

Here, we present the Irish Water Quality Index (IEWQI) model for assessing transitional and coastal water quality in an effort to improve the method and develop a tool that can be used by environmental regulators to abate water pollution in Ireland. The developed model has been associated with the adoption of water quality standards formulated for coastal and transitional waterbodies according to the water framework directive legislation by the environmental regulator of Irish water. The model consists of five identical components, including (i) indicator selection technique is to select the crucial water quality indicator; (ii) sub-index (SI) function for rescaling various water quality indicators' information into a uniform scale; (iii) indicators' weight method for estimating the weight values based on the relative significance of real-time information on water quality; (iii) aggregation function for computing the water quality index (WQI) score; and (v) score interpretation scheme for assessing the state of water quality. The IEWQI model was developed based on Cork Harbour, Ireland. The developed IEWQI model was applied to four coastal waterbodies in Ireland, for assessing water quality using 2021 water quality data for the summer and winter seasons in order to evaluate model sensitivity in terms of spatio-temporal resolution of various waterbodies. The model efficiency and uncertainty were also analysed in this research. In terms of different spatio-temporal magnitudes of various domains, the model shows higher sensitivity in four application domains during the summer and winter. In addition, the results of uncertainty reveal that the IEWQI model architecture may be effective for reducing model uncertainty in order to avoid model eclipsing and ambiguity problems. The findings of this study reveal that the IEWQI model could be an efficient and reliable technique for the assessment of transitional and coastal water quality more accurately in any geospatial domain.

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1. Introduction

Water is an essential component of the environment, but environmental sustainability is dependent on “good” water quality. Surface water is one crucial resource for the management of aquatic ecosystems and their components (Parween et al., 2022; Uddin et al., 2017, 2018, 2021, 2022a). Unfortunately, gradually, the surface water quality has been degraded due to the association of various natural, like hydrological, climatic, topographical, lithological, etc., and anthropogenic events, such as agricultural activities, mining, production and disposal of waste from various sources like industries, municipal activities, domestic waste, medical waste, etc. (Uddin et al., 2016, 2020a, 2021). In that case, it is very hard to keep all bodies of water in “good” water quality (Uddin et al., 2022a).

For the purpose of maintaining a “good” state of water quality in all states, a number of tools and techniques have been developed by various countries/organizations/agencies. For example, the water framework directive was formulated in 2000 to keep “good” water quality within the extents of European countries (Zotou et al., 2018). The water framework directive is one kind of policy that guides a set of rules and regulations on how to obtain the goals of the framework. But, the framework does not refer to any specific tools or techniques for achieving “good” water quality (Carsten Von Der Ohe et al., 2007; Uddin et al., 2022a). Consequently, the EU countries have been striving for the optimization of a technique in order to assess water quality more accurately, which technique could be adopted by all EU countries as a “universal” technique (Carsten Von Der Ohe et al., 2007). In terms of global aspects, similar problems have been experienced in the rest of the world. They have been trying to explore the best solution for achieving a “good” state of water quality in all waterbodies (Carsten Von Der Ohe et al., 2007; Uddin et al., 2022a; Zotou et al., 2018).

Currently, most of the countries widely used very typical monitoring approach for assessing water quality due to a few constraints of this technique. It has received much more criticisms for its technical aspects and data accuracy (Strobl and Robillard, 2008). Recently, several studies have reported that the traditional monitoring program is not affordable for both developing and developed countries due to a few basic requirements, like the need for highly equipped and advanced laboratory facilities, skilled manpower, sufficient funding, etc. (Sutadian et al., 2017; Uddin et al., 2022a). Moreover, this technique is a very expensive and time-consuming approach (Jiang et al., 2020; Strobl and Robillard, 2008).

Consequently, to date, different hydrological models have been utilized for assessing surface water quality (lake, river, transitional, coastal, etc.). The water quality index (WQI) model is one of them. Horton first introduced it in 1960 for assessing the river water quality (Uddin et al., 2021; Horton, 1965). The WQI method is a point-based rapid assessment technique that converts a series of water quality data into a single numerical expression. Since then, this technique has become a widely used technique for assessing water quality (surface, groundwater, etc.) by following a few common frameworks. To date, several WQI models have been developed by various organizations/countries/researchers for assessing water quality, specially they are focused on specific domains or waterbodies like lakes, rivers, groundwater, mine water, wastewater, etc. To the best of the author's knowledge, there are no existing WQI models focused on coastal water quality, but a few studies have utilized common WQI models like the NSF index (Gupta et al., 2003; Jha et al., 2015), the CCME index (de Rosemond et al., 2009), and modified NSF WQI (Ma et al., 2020) for assessing coastal water quality. In earlier studies and a literature review, the authors discussed the details of various WQI models' histories, architectures, components, and applications in order to develop a WQI model focused on coastal water quality. Details of the study can be found in Uddin et al., 2021.

Based on the model architecture, it typically consists of five identical components, including (i) **the indicators selection process** used to select the crucial water quality indicators in terms of their relative significance; (ii) **sub-index functions** that allow to transfer various water quality data into the unit less form without hiding any real information about indicators; (iii) **weight generation technique** mainly used for assigning the

importance of indicators based on their influential capabilities of water quality; (iv) **the aggregation function** that is provided to convert sub-index and weighting values into the single numerical number that is called “WQI score”, and (v) **the classification scheme** is used to interpret the WQI score in order to classify the water quality as “good”, “fair”, “marginal” etc. The existing WQI models have received much more criticism with regard to their reliability and accuracy. Recently, several studies have revealed that the entire models have contributed a significant amount of uncertainty to the final assessment of water quality. A number of studies have reported that each component of the model produces its own uncertainty (Uddin et al., 2021, 2022c, 2022d, 2022e).

Recently, several studies have revealed that the WQI model has produced a significant amount of uncertainty from the various components of this model (Uddin et al., 2022a, 2022b). Many researchers have argued that a considerable amount of uncertainty is contributed to the WQI model by the indicators' selection process, sub-index functions, and inappropriate aggregation functions (Sutadian et al., 2017; Uddin et al., 2021, 2022a, 2022c). Moreover, a few studies have revealed that the weighting technique also provided a considerable uncertainty to the final assessment. Considering all the findings in the literature, in recent years, the authors have carried out several studies in terms of investigating the appropriate technique for selecting crucial indicators, sub-index functions, weighting techniques, aggregation functions, classification schemes, sources of uncertainty, or inappropriateness of the model outcomes in order to develop an improved model for assessing transitional and coastal waters by the following studies:

- (i) Model development history, nature, architecture, applications, using tools and techniques, sources of uncertainties, ambiguity, the eclipsing problem, classification schemes, etc. has been published in Uddin et al. (2021).
- (ii) Analysed the sensitivity of various established WQI models for assessing coastal water quality in terms of geospatial regulation in Uddin et al. (2020a).
- (iii) Analysed various existing models performance for assessing coastal water quality in Uddin et al. (2020b).
- (iv) Based on the existing problems, the authors proposed an improved methodology for developing a water quality index model with completely new sub-index functions, a new approach for estimating weight values, a new aggregation function, and a new classification scheme for coastal water in Uddin et al. (2022a).
- (v) Optimization algorithm(s) for predicting the weighted quadratic mean (WQM)-WQI architecture in order to reduce model uncertainty in Uddin et al. (2022b).
- (vi) In terms of model uncertainty, the authors have been carried out another study on estimating uncertainty at each step of improved WQI model and compared with existing seven established models using machine learning approach for determining the scenarios of uncertainty of various model in Uddin et al. (2022c).
- (vii) In order to select the crucial indicators, the authors proposed the random forest algorithm after revising the improved model in Uddin et al. (2022d).
- (viii) A number of studies have revealed that the existing WQI model provides improper classes due to its inappropriate classification schemes. The authors revised existing classification schemes and analysed model performance using a proposed classification scheme for coastal water quality incorporating four widely used machine learning classifiers in Uddin et al. (2022e).
- (ix) For the purposes of determining the uncertainty production rate of the various weighting techniques, the authors compared four widely used subjective based mathematical techniques in Uddin et al. (2022g).

It should be noted that the investigation studies mentioned above were conducted in Cork Harbour, Ireland (see Fig. 1B), with a particular emphasis on the quality of the transitional and coastal waters. After conducting the aforementioned studies, the authors of this paper would like to propose a

more accurate and improved WQI model for evaluating transitional and coastal water quality. This model could be referred to as the “**Irish Water Quality Index Model**,” also abbreviated as “**IEWQI**”. The proposed IEWQI model consists of five components, which are as follows:

- (i) For the optimization of model input, the random forest algorithm has been recommended for the IEWQI.
- (ii) Three newly developed linear interpolation rescaling functions have been proposed for computing the sub-index of the IEWQI.
- (iii) In order to estimate the accurate weight values of indicators, a comprehensive approach combining the random forest technique incorporating with the mathematical function of the rank sum technique proposed for the IEWQI.
- (iv) To compute the WQI scores more accurately, a completely new weighted quadratic mean (WQM) function has been introduced as the “aggregation function” of the IEWQI.
- (v) A brand new classification scheme including four identical water classes like “good”, “fair”, “marginal”, and “poor” has been suggested for assessing coastal water quality using the IEWQI.

The present paper is structured as follows: [Section 2](#) provides a short description of the model application domains, [Section 3](#) describes in detail the IEWQI model components and model validation techniques, [Section 4](#) provides the details of the analytical procedures for model sensitivity, [Section 5](#) presents results and discussion of the IEWQI model, sensitivity, efficiency, and model uncertainty, [Section 6](#) presents the application results of the IEWQI model for assessing transitional and coastal water quality in four selected domains in Ireland, [Section 7](#) summarizes the findings and recommendations.

2. Model application domains

The present study selected four application domains that cover the entire extent of the transitional and coastal waterbodies in Ireland in order to assess the sensitivity of the model in terms of spatiotemporal resolution. The following are the selected four coastal waterbodies:

(i) **Dublin Bay** is located on the east coast of Ireland (see [Fig. 1A](#)). This bay is primarily used for international navigation, and it is where Dublin Port is located. In Dublin Bay, the river Liffey is one of the most significant inflow rivers so far. Relatively, Dublin Bay is well known as a commercial hub of Ireland, and the surrounding hinterland is dominated by the various economic, industrial, and agricultural activities that directly influence the bay's water quality ([Wall et al., 2020](#)). Recently, a few studies have revealed that the Dublin Bay has received around 8.875 million cubic meters square of untreated sewage and storm water between 2017 and 2020 ([Environmental Protection Agency, 2020](#)). Due to the wastewater and storm water discharged into Dublin Bay from the treatment plant, Bay water quality has degraded significantly in the last few years ([Dublin Port Company, 2021](#); [Environmental Protection Agency, 2020](#));

(ii) **Cork Harbour** is located on the southwest coast and the largest Harbour in Ireland (see [Fig. 1B](#)). Several major tributary rivers which flows into the mainstream the Harbour ([Hartnett and Nash, 2015](#); [Uddin et al., 2022a](#));

(iii) **Galway Bay** is situated on the southeast coast and is one of the longest catchment areas in Ireland, whereas the largest urban centre in the catchment is the eastern part of Galway City (see [Fig. 1C](#)). A number of rivers are included in this catchment area, like the Athenry, Louyghrea, Gort, and Oranmore. Recently, several studies have reported that the Galway Bay receives a significant amount of domestic waste each year, which has a significant impact on the water quality of the bay ([Donnelly, 2017](#); [Environmental Protection Agency, 2020](#)); and

(iv) **Mulroy Bay** - is the most convoluted of the marine inlets and is located on the north-west coast of Ireland (see [Fig. 1D](#)). This Bay is particularly important for aquaculture, particularly salmon farming, and for scallop spat collection. Recently, a few studies have addressed the impacts of aquaculture on water quality in Mulroy Bay, but there is no significant issue at the current pressure level of farming. Although, the EPA reported

that a number of pressures, like domestic waste, and agricultural pressures are impacting the water quality in this Bay.

3. Methods and materials

3.1. Data descriptions

For the purposes of the present study, water quality data for selected four domains were retrieved from the monitoring database of the Irish Environmental Protection Agency (EPA). Usually, the EPA throughout the year monitors water quality frequently at approximately high and low tides across the different waterbodies like the Lake River, Harbour, Bay etc. in Ireland. For the purposes of sensitivity analysis of the IEWQI model in terms of the spatio-temporal resolution, the present study used 2021 monitored water quality data and data divided into two seasons, including (i) summer (April–September), and (ii) winter (October–February). Data for indicators was obtained from Dublin Bay, Cork Harbour, Galway Bay, and Mulroy Bay, respectively, twenty-four, thirty-seven, twenty-two, and fourteen monitoring sites were selected based on the availability of a full suite of indicators that required this analysis and coverage of the full extent of the application domain. Details of the monitoring sites and their geographical locations can be found in [Table S1](#). For consistency of data, only 1 m depth samples from the water surface were considered in this research. Details of the data attributes can be found at <https://www.catchments.ie/data>.

In total, nine water quality indicators were used in this research, whereas six common indicators included salinity (SAL), dissolved oxygen (DOX), biological oxygen demand (BOD₅), pH, water temperature (TEMP), transparency (TRAN), and three nutrient enrichment indicators included total oxidized nitrogen (TON), dissolved inorganic nitrogen (DIN), and molybdate reactive phosphorus (MRP). The depth average and seasonal average concentration of water quality indicators for each monitoring site were obtained by calculating the mean of monitored concentrations in a certain season (summer or winter). Details of the water quality indicator concentration at each monitoring site can be found in [Table S2](#). It is noted that the SAL concentration is only used to determine the guideline values (moving thresholds) for the nutrient enrichment indicators (MRP, DOX, and DIN) using the median value according to the methodology of [Uddin et al. \(2022a\)](#). [Table S10](#) provides the details of the moving thresholds for a certain median value of SAL. A statistical summary of SAL concentration across the four domains is presented in [Fig. 2](#) below.

3.2. Irish Water Quality Index (IEWQI) model

Here, we presented the details of the IEWQI model components. Like other established WQI models, the IEWQI model consists of five identical elements. There are: (i) indicators selection technique; (ii) sub-index functions; (iii) weight value obtaining technique; (iv) aggregation function; and (v) IEWQI score interpretation framework. [Fig. 3](#) provides the fundamental architecture of the IEWQI model. Details of each component are described below in systematic order.

3.2.1. Indicators selection technique

The WQI indicator selection technique is the primary component of the WQI model that is used to select the crucial indicators for the input of the WQI model ([Parween et al., 2022](#); [Uddin et al., 2022a](#); [Uddin et al., 2022f](#); [Uddin et al., 2021](#)). Currently, a number of tools and techniques, including principal component analysis ([Guo et al., 2002](#); [Parween et al., 2022](#); [Tao et al., 2016](#); [Uddin et al., 2022a](#)), correlation technique ([Ibrahim et al., 2021](#); [Kumar and Chong, 2018](#)), Delphi technique ([Almeida et al., 2012](#); [Mladenović-Ranisavljević and Žerajić, 2018](#); [Neary et al., 2001](#); [Smith, 1990](#)), expert panel judgement ([House, 1980, 1990](#)), analytical hierarchical process ([Sutadian et al., 2018](#), [Sutadian et al., 2017](#)), data availability ([Sutadian et al., 2018](#); [Thi Minh Hanh et al., 2010](#)), based on environmental significance of indicators ([Horton, 1965](#); [Liou et al., 2004](#); [Said et al., 2004](#)) etc., are widely used for selecting the

Fig. 2. A statistical overview of SAL concentration across a range of application domains in Ireland.

important water quality indicators in considering the relative importance of indicators in literature (Gupta and Gupta, 2021; Uddin et al., 2021). In an earlier review study, the authors identified a range of techniques that are widely utilized in order to extract the importance indicator in existing

WQI models. The details of the findings of this critical review can be found in Uddin et al. (2021). Recently, several studies have revealed that the entire indicator selection technique contributed a significant amount of uncertainty to the final assessment due to the inappropriate indicator

Fig. 3. Proposed fundamental architecture for the Irish water quality index model.

selection (Gupta and Gupta, 2021; Parween et al., 2022; Sutadian et al., 2016; Uddin et al., 2022a, 2022d). In order to reduce the model uncertainty through the indicator selection process, a few studies have utilized different machine learning algorithms like random forest, support vector machine, tree algorithm, gradient boosting algorithm, k-nearest neighbour, artificial neural network, etc. to avoid human or expert intervention in this process (Geurts et al., 2006; Islam Khan et al., 2022, Islam Khan et al., 2021; Touzani et al., 2018; Uddin et al., 2022b, 2022e, Uddin et al., 2022c; Vergara and Estévez, 2014).

In a recent study, the authors used the gradient boosting algorithm by comparing the performance of four widely used machine-learning techniques in order to select important indicators of coastal waters (Uddin et al., 2022a). This study has suggested that the gradient boosting algorithm is effective for selecting crucial water quality indicators in terms of the relative significance of variables. Details of the findings of this research can be found in Uddin et al. (2022a). Many studies have also recommended the gradient boosting algorithm for selecting important indicators for other waterbodies like lakes, rivers, etc., in a given dataset (Huan et al., 2020; Islam Khan et al., 2022; Naghibi et al., 2020; Touzani et al., 2018; Uddin et al., 2022d, 2022f). In terms of the reliability of this technique, a few studies reveal that the gradient boosting algorithm does not reflect the actual scenarios of significant indicators that express the relative value of the indicators in terms of influencing coastal water quality (Uddin et al., 2022a, 2022d). Moreover, a few studies have reported that the gradient boosting algorithm shows an over fitting problem in predicting important features (Ahmed et al., 2019; Islam Khan et al., 2021; Uddin et al., 2022b, 2022d). Consequently, recently, the authors have carried out a comprehensive assessment of eighteen feature selection algorithms to select important indicators for assessing coastal water quality and have analysed the reliability of these techniques (Uddin et al., 2022d).

Uddin et al. (2022d) have revealed that the random forest algorithm is effective for selecting important water quality indicators in terms of justifying the reliability of the selected indicators that influence coastal water quality. In addition, this study also showed that, compared to other techniques, random forest techniques could significantly reduce the model uncertainty (Alnahit et al., 2022; Uddin et al., 2022d). Details of the findings of this study can be found in Uddin et al. (2022d). Moreover, many water

research and machine learning studies have also suggested this technique for choosing the key features in a provided dataset in order to develop an accurate prediction model, whereas the selected features can represent the overall attributes of data in a database (Alnahit et al., 2022; Hou et al., 2022; Jović et al., 2015; Malek et al., 2022). The present study used the random forest technique for selecting the crucial water quality indicators according to the methodology of Uddin et al. (2022d). Details of the algorithm, model optimized hyperparameters, and model performance can be found in Uddin et al. (2022d). The random forest technique is one of the most widely used state-of-the-art tree-based algorithms that applies multiple base models using subsets of the given data, whereas model decisions are made based on the average of each individual tree decision (Ali Khan et al., 2022; Malek et al., 2022; Xu et al., 2021). Details of the algorithm architecture can be found in Liaw and Wiener (2002). Table 1 and Table 4 provide the selected eight water quality indicators obtained from the random forest technique, unites, and their standard threshold for assessing coastal water quality and rank of them, respectively.

3.2.2. Sub-index functions

Sub-index (SI) functions are used to transfer various water quality indicators into the uniform scale without hiding/losing any actual information about water quality (Uddin et al., 2021, 2022a). Different approaches are used for computing the SI values in the literature by existing WQI models (Gupta and Gupta, 2021; Uddin et al., 2022a, 2022d). For the purposes of obtaining the SI values, a few WQIs are used as indicators of concentration directly as SI values (Dinius, 1987; Horton, 1965; Liou et al., 2004; Said et al., 2004; Štambuk-Giljanović, 2003), some indices are used liner interpolated functions (Misaghi et al., 2017; Parween et al., 2022; Sutadian et al., 2018; Tomas et al., 2017; Uddin et al., 2021, 2022a), and several models are widely used the rating curve functions (Almeida et al., 2012; Fathi et al., 2022; Sim et al., 2015), respectively. Commonly, it ranges from 0 to 100, where 0 refers “poor” and 100 indicates “excellent” water quality, respectively (Uddin et al., 2021, 2022a).

Recently, several studies have revealed that the SI functions contribute a significant amount of uncertainty in the final assessment of water quality (Gupta and Gupta, 2021; Sutadian et al., 2016; Uddin et al., 2021, 2022b). In an earlier study, the authors revealed that the existing SI

Table 1
Standard thresholds (guideline) of water quality indicators for coastal water quality.

	Indicators	unit	Standard threshold (summer)		Standard threshold (winter)	
			Lower	Upper	Lower	Upper
(i) Constant thresholds for common indicators	BOD5 ⁽ⁱⁱ⁾	mg/l	0	7	0	7
	pH ⁽ⁱⁱⁱ⁾	–	5	9	5	9
	TEMP ^(iv)	°C	–	25	–	25
	TON ^(iv)	mg/l as N	0.0	2	0.0	2
	TRAN ^(v)	m/depth	>1	–	>1	–
(ii) Moving thresholds for nutrient enrichment indicators			<i>thresholds for SAL median value of 31</i>		<i>thresholds for SAL median value of 29</i>	
(a) Dublin Bay	DOX ⁽ⁱ⁾	% sat	78	122	77	123
	MRP ⁽ⁱ⁾	mg/l as P	0.0	0.044	0.0	0.047
	DIN ⁽ⁱ⁾	mg/l	0.0	0.51	0.0	0.633
			<i>thresholds for SAL median value of 31</i>		<i>thresholds for SAL median value of 18</i>	
(b) Cork Harbour	DOX ⁽ⁱ⁾	% sat	78	122	71	129
	MRP ⁽ⁱ⁾	mg/l as P	0.0	0.044	0.0	0.059
	DIN ⁽ⁱ⁾	mg/l	0.0	0.51	0.0	1.336
			<i>thresholds for SAL median value of 29</i>		<i>thresholds for SAL median value of 26</i>	
(c) Galway Bay	DOX ⁽ⁱ⁾	% sat	77	123	75	125
	MRP ⁽ⁱ⁾	mg/l as P	0.0	0.047	0.0	0.050
	DIN ⁽ⁱ⁾	mg/l	0.0	0.630	0.0	0.825
			<i>thresholds for SAL median value of 33</i>		<i>thresholds for SAL median value of 30</i>	
(d) Mulroy Bay	DOX ⁽ⁱ⁾	% sat	79	121	77	123
	MRP ⁽ⁱ⁾	mg/l as P	0.0	0.042	0.0	0.046
	DIN ⁽ⁱ⁾	mg/l	0.0	0.380	0.0	0.57

1. ATSEBI standards, determine the standard values based on median value of Salinity (see details (Toner et al., 2005), pp. 72–76).
 2. EPA, Ireland (2001), recommended values for the surface water/freshwater/river water/aquatic life.
 3. Estuary Monitoring Manual for pH and Alkalinity, EPA,USA
 4. The European Communities (Quality of surface water intended for the abstraction of drinking water) regulations, 1989 (S.I. No. 294/1989).
 5. Bathing Water Quality Regulations 2008, (S.I. No. 79/2008).

techniques have suffered from eclipsing problems that may contribute to a considerable amount of the uncertainty in WQI results (Uddin et al., 2022a). The eclipsing refers to the inappropriate rescaling issue with the function(s), which arises when the function(s) either compute lower SI value (“poor” quality) without any input of indicators that are not exceeding the critical threshold or compute higher SI values (“excellent” quality) with the input of a few indicators that exceed the range of the critical threshold of the indicator (s). Details of the ambiguity, its nature, and measurement methodology can be found in Uddin et al. (2022a). Recently, the authors developed and validated three entirely new linear interpolation rescaling functions to compute SI values more accurately for different water quality indicators, avoiding the ambiguity issues in the WQI model (Uddin et al., 2022a). The appropriate SI function(s) for each indicator is adopted based on a few binary rules. Details of the binary rules for determining the correct SI function(s) can be found in Table 2.

The present study introduced three completely new SI functions for the IEWQI model. SI values for selected indicators were computed using the Eqs. (1) to (3) according to the improved methodology of Uddin et al. (2020a), whereas the indicator(s) threshold range was obtained from Table 1 (above).

$$SI = (SI_u - SI_l) - \frac{(SI_u \times WQ_m)}{(STD_u - STD_l)} \tag{1}$$

$$SI = \frac{(WQ_m - STD_l)}{(STD_u - STD_l)} \times SI_u \tag{2}$$

$$SI_i = (SI_u - SI_l) - \frac{(WQ_m - STD_l)}{(STD_u - STD_l)} \tag{3}$$

where, SI is sub-index value of indicator(s), SI_u is threshold upper value (100 for “excellent”) of the respective water class, SI_l is threshold lower value (0 for “poor”) of the respective water class, STD_u is threshold upper limit of the standard for regarding indicator, STD_l is threshold lower limit of the standard for regarding indicator, and WQ_m is the measured or actual concentration of water quality indicator. Details of the threshold ranges can be found in table 1.

3.2.3. Obtaining indicators weight values

The indicator weighting technique is another crucial component in the development of the WQI model. Commonly, weight generation techniques are used to estimate the weight values of water quality indicators that should reflect the relative importance of indicators in the WQI model (Uddin et al., 2022b; Uddin et al., 2022a; Uddin et al., 2021).

The existing WQI system uses a variety of tools and techniques, including subjective method that are driven by professionals or decision makers [like expert judgement (Singh et al., 2018; Sutadian et al., 2018), Delphi method (Dadolahi-Sohrab et al., 2012), etc.], objective methods that associated with a number of mathematical functions that estimate indicator weight values without requiring human involvement (such as the entropy method, rank sum technique, rank order centroid technique, equal or

Table 2

Binary rules for determining the SI functions for various water quality indicators according to Uddin et al. (2022a).

Indicators	Conditions	Sub-index functions
BOD ₅ , MRP, DIN, TON DOX	–	Eq. (1)
	(i) if DOX > 100	Eq. (2)
	(ii) if, DOX < 100	Eq. (2)
	(iii) if, DOX = 100	SI = 100
pH	(i) If, pH ≥ 5.0 and pH < 7.5	Eq. (2)
	(ii) If, pH > 8.5 and pH ≤ 9.0	Eq. (3)
	(iii) If, pH ≥ 7.5 and pH ≤ 8.5	100
TEMP	(i) If, TEMP ≤ 25	100
	(ii) If, TEMP > 25	0.0
TRAN	(i) If. TRAN < 1.0	Eq. (3)
	(ii) If. TRAN ≥ 1.0	100

unequal weighting methods), and hybrid methods (like the analytical hierarchy process, the most widely used technique have been utilized for estimating indicator weight values (Sutadian et al., 2017).

Recently, several studies have revealed that the existing weighting approaches have contributed to a significant amount of uncertainty in water quality assessment due to inappropriate weight estimation (Uddin et al., 2022a, 2022c; Uddin et al., 2021). A few studies have also reported that the WQI model produced a considerable amount of uncertainty due to its subjective based weighting system (Uddin et al., 2022a, 2022b). Moreover, the authors have conducted another critical review study on the WQI models recently. This study has also addressed a list of current weighting techniques, broadly discussed their pros and cons, and examined their impacts on the WQI system in terms of producing model uncertainty. Details of the study are discussed in Uddin et al. (2021). In addition, most studies have utilized state-of-the-art machine learning techniques for estimating the feature weight values based on their relative importance in machine learning studies.

Given the current state of various weighting techniques, the authors recently proposed a novel weighting approach that allows for the incorporation of machine learning techniques and objective-based mathematical functions (Uddin et al., 2022a). This approach consist of two sub-sequential processes, (i) ranking indicators based on their relative importance using machine learning techniques; and (ii) estimating weight values of indicators using an objective based rank order centroid technique (Uddin et al., 2022a). The details of the methodology can be found in Uddin et al. (2022a). In an earlier study, the authors also compared various objective based weighting techniques and evaluated their performance in terms of contributing uncertainty to the model. This study revealed that there were no significant differences across the ranks based on various weighting functions (Uddin et al., 2022g). For the purposes of estimating indicator weight values more accurately, the present study utilized the approach of Uddin et al. (2022a). A tree-based random forest machine learning technique is used to rank indicators of water quality in order to accurately estimate the weight values of each indicator in relation to their relative importance. The authors' recent study has revealed that the random forest algorithm is a reliable technique for ranking water quality indicators that accurately reflects the relative information of indicators. Details of this study can be found in Uddin et al. (2022d). Finally, the objectively based rank sum mathematical function used to estimate the weight values of indicators outperformed the other methods in terms of reducing model uncertainty in the WQI model (Uddin et al., 2022g). Moreover, recently, many studies have reported that this technique is more reliable and effective than other objective methods in estimating weight values accurately (Li et al., 2009; Odu, 2019; Roszkowska, 2013; Song and Kang, 2016). It can be defined as follows:

$$\text{Rank sum method : } w_i = \frac{n + 1 - i}{\sum_{j=1}^n j} = \frac{2(n + 1 - i)}{n(n + 1)}, i = 1, 2, 3, \dots, n \tag{4}$$

where n is the total number of ranked indicators; i is the i^{th} indicator rank; j is the summation of rank and w is the weight value.

3.2.4. Aggregation function

Aggregation function is the final component of the WQI model. It allows converting the SI and weight values of various water quality indicators into a numerical value that is well known as the WQI index or WQI score(s). Commonly, the aggregation functions can be classified into two groups: (i) weighted functions (which require estimation of indicator weight values), and (ii) unweighted functions (not require indicator weight formulation and only use the SI values). Up to date, different aggregation functions have been used in entire WQI approaches including arithmetic including additive (Horton, 1965) and multiplicative (Alphayo and Sharma, 2018; Asadollah et al., 2021; Gradilla-Hernández et al., 2020; Mladenović-Ranisavljević and Žerajić, 2018; Parween et al., 2022; Tomas et al., 2017; Zotou et al., 2019), geometric (Sutadian et al., 2017; Thi Minh Hanh et al., 2010), combined approaches: combination of arithmetic

and geometric (Almeida et al., 2012; Bordalo et al., 2006; Cude, 2001; Dadolahi-Sohrab et al., 2012), and minimum operator functions (Smith, 1990) etc. Details of the various aggregation functions, mathematical expressions, and their applications can be found in Uddin et al. (2021).

Recently, several studies have revealed that the existing aggregation functions contribute a significant amount of uncertainty to the final assessment due to the inappropriate aggregation process. In an earlier study, the authors revealed that the existing aggregation functions have been influenced by the ambiguity problem (Gupta and Gupta, 2021; Uddin et al., 2022a). Ambiguity is another great concern that could have contributed to the considerable amount of uncertainty in the final assessment by hiding the real state of water quality that is contained in the model inputs (Uddin et al., 2022a). As a consequence, that led to the misclassification of water quality for environmental managers or assessors. It can be categorized into two types: overestimating and underestimating ambiguity, which are associated with the inappropriate aggregation process. Details of the ambiguity problems of the aggregation process are briefly discussed in Uddin et al. (2021, 2022a). In their recent study, the authors compared eight aggregation functions, including four weighted and four unweighted, whereas five are established functions that are widely used in the existing WQI approaches, and three (one weighted and two unweighted) were newly proposed for the purposes of comparing the model performance. Details of the findings can be found in Uddin et al. (2022a). In terms of model uncertainty, Uddin et al. (2022a) have revealed that the newly proposed weighted quadratic mean (WQM) and unweighted root mean squared (RMS) aggregation functions showed the best outperformance in assessing coastal water quality. Relatively, both functions have been found to be free from these issues (both types of ambiguity), while the majority of commonly used techniques, like the CCME, SRDD, WJ, etc., have been significantly influenced by the ambiguity problems (Uddin et al., 2022a).

Moreover, another earlier study by the authors revealed that the WQM and RMS functions are effective for computing the WQI score in order to reduce the model uncertainty. Also, these functions are highly efficient for reducing model ambiguity and eclipsing problems significantly (Uddin et al., 2022c). According to their research, these aggregation functions produce <2 % of uncertainty during the aggregation process, compared to nearly or >10 % of uncertainty produced by other existing techniques. Details of the findings of uncertainty for various aggregation functions can be found in Uddin et al. (2022c). To the best of the author's knowledge, the earlier mentioned studies are the first initiatives to analyse and estimate model uncertainty at each step of the WQI process for different models. In that case, most aggregation functions do not enable the expression of the actual water quality information. Consequently, the existing functions provide a significant amount of uncertainty in the final assessment (Gupta and Gupta, 2021; Uddin et al., 2021, 2022a, 2022b). Therefore, for the purposes of the aggregation of SI and weight value(s), the present study utilized the weight quadratic mean (WQM) aggregation function for the computation of the WQI index for the IEWQI model. It can be defined as follows:

$$IEWQI = \sqrt{\sum_{i=1}^n w_i s_i^2} \quad (5)$$

where s_i is the sub-index value for indicator i ; w_i is weight value of respective indicators and n is the number of indicators.

3.2.5. Evaluation of IEWQI model outcomes

The ultimate goal of the IEWQI model is to classify the water quality using a classification scheme. Commonly, the WQI model's final output is a numerical value called an "index score", that ranges between 0 (poor quality) and 100 (good quality). For the interpretation of the WQI score, the existing WQI system used a range of classification schemes in the literature (Uddin et al., 2021). Recently, several studies have revealed that a significant amount of uncertainty has been produced due to inappropriate classification schemes. Consequently, the typical classification schemes can provide inconsistent results in the final assessment of water quality

for similar groups of water quality indicators (Uddin et al., 2022a, 2022e). Moreover, recently many studies have reported that the widely used classification scheme "One Out-All Out" of the water framework directive has also received much more criticism due to the inaccurate classification of water quality (Latinopoulos et al., 2021; Prato et al., 2014). Therefore, in order to avoid this inaccurate assessment, the authors have proposed a universal classification scheme for assessing coastal and transitional water quality in an earlier study (Uddin et al., 2022a). Uddin et al. (2022a) have revealed that the results of water quality assessing using the universal scheme reflect the accurate scenarios of water quality. In this research, the IEWQI model output was interpreted using the classification approach of Uddin et al. (2022a). Table 3 provides the classification schemes and their definitions for the quality of coastal water. Details of the classification procedures can be found in Uddin et al. (2022a).

4. Model sensitivity analysis

4.1. Machine learning approaches

Machine learning is an advanced, state-of-the-art technology that is widely used to predict or classify unknown objects based on the previous learning model (Uddin et al., 2022b). Recently, this technique has been most widely utilized for evaluating the sensitivity of water quality models in terms of the accurate assessment of water quality or classification. The present study used the multilinear regression (MLR) machine learning algorithm for evaluating the IEWQI model's sensitivity according to the approach of Uddin et al. (2022a). Details of the methodology for the MLR analysis can be found in Uddin et al. (2022a). In earlier studies, many researchers successfully utilized this technique in order to investigate the effect of model predictors (water quality indicators) on the response (IEWQI score) in water quality research (Chaudhary and Hantush, 2017; Rahman, 2019; Uddin et al., 2022a). The model sensitivity was assessed by comparing the coefficient of determination (R^2) between the IEWQI scores and the MLR predicted scores using the same water quality indicators for both techniques. In this research, the MLR algorithm has been performed using the regression learner apps with MATLAB R2022a. Details of the regression learner apps and their applications can be found in Uddin et al. (2022c).

4.1.1. Model evaluation

Once the MLR prediction model was developed, the model's performance was evaluated using various performance metrics. The present study used root mean square error (RMSE), mean square error (MSE), and mean absolute error (MAE) to assess the performance of the regression model because; most studies in water research have widely used these metrics to assess prediction models using machine learning and artificial intelligence techniques (Asadollah et al., 2021; Uddin et al., 2022b; Uddin et al., 2022a; Zaghoul and Achari, 2022). To estimate the performance criteria, the cross-validation technique is widely used in machine learning and artificial intelligence regression models. In this research, the 10-fold cross-validation technique was performed using the approaches of Uddin et al. (2022a) and Uddin et al. (2022b). The performance criteria score

Table 3

Classification scheme for coastal water quality of Uddin et al. (2022a).

Classes	WQI score	Definition
Good	80–100	Good waterbodies that meet the standard values and thus water quality is suitable for all use.
Fair	50–79	Waterbodies that a few indicators meet the standard values and the water quality is usually protected with a minor degree of impairment.
Marginal	30–49	The majority of the water quality indicators failed to meet the criteria; water quality in unprotected, which may be posing a risk for aquatic life.
Poor	0–29	Poor waterbodies are those that failed to meet all the criteria; water quality is completely unprotected and unsuitable for many specific usages.

typically ranges from 0 to 1, with all criteria expecting a score as low as possible. The lowest score indicates the best model performance.

4.2. Model efficiency analysis

For the purposes of model efficiency analysis, a range of statistical and mathematical tools and techniques are used; the Nash–Sutcliffe efficiency (NSE) index is one of them (McCuen et al., 2006; McManus et al., 2020). Recently, several scientific studies in various domains have utilized this technique for assessing the model's performance in terms of efficiently predicting (Chaudhary and Hantush, 2017; Rahman, 2020; Rahman and Harding, 2016; Uddin et al., 2022d). It allows measuring and determining the magnitude of residual variation in a comparison to recorded data variance (Izhar Shah et al., 2021; Minh et al., 2022). Details of the NSE index can be found in McCuen et al. (2006). The NSE score typically ranges from $-\infty$ to 1, with a score close to 1 indicating the best model performance and a negative score indicating poor model performance (Sharif et al., 2022; Uddin et al., 2022d). Moreover, a few studies have proposed the model efficiency factor (MEF) in order to analyse the model efficiency more reliably (Sharif et al., 2022). This technique is an extended form of the NSE index and is a more comprehensive and reliable tool than other techniques. In recent studies have utilized this method successfully in water research to identify the best prediction model in terms of the prediction errors (Uddin et al., 2022d). Like the NSE score, the MEF scores also

ranged between 0 and 1, where 0 refers to the bias free model and 1 indicates the lowest efficiency of the model, respectively (McCuen et al., 2006; Sharif et al., 2022; Uddin et al., 2022d). These techniques were used in this study to assess the IEWQI model's efficiency in terms of reliable water assessment. Details of these techniques are discussed in Uddin et al. (2022d).

4.3. Uncertainty analysis

Uncertainty estimation is an important component of any mathematical or computational model. Because it provides a concrete idea of exactly how much data inconsistency the model has produced, which could be helpful for the improvement of the model architecture (Liang et al., 2016; Uddin et al., 2022c). Recently, the WQI model has received much more criticism due to the uncertainty issues. In an earlier study, the authors compared five existing WQI models with the improved methodology. This study reported that the improved methodology produced the least uncertainty compared to other traditional approaches. Details of this study can be found in Uddin et al. (2022a). Therefore, the present study used this improved technique for assessing coastal water quality in Ireland in order to estimate the uncertainty and compare it in terms of the spatio-temporal resolution of application domains. For the purposes of estimating uncertainty, the present study used the inferential error bar analysis approach by following the approach of Uddin et al. (2022c), because several studies have been carried

Fig. 4. Statistical summary for selected water quality indicators over the four application domains in Ireland, whereas S and W on the x-axes refer to summer and winter, respectively.

out using this approach for estimating and modeling the data uncertainty in measuring value (Commowick and Warfield, 2010; Cumming et al., 2007; Cumming and Finch, 2005; Jolliffe, 2007). Details of the methodology are discussed in (Uddin et al., 2022c). Moreover, recently, a few water research studies have utilized this technique for modeling the expected amount of uncertainty in a measurement using the predicted interval of WQI scores. In this research, both MLR predicted IEWQI scores and WQM aggregation scores have been used for modeling the amount of uncertainty in both the WQM aggregation function and prediction scores, respectively (Krueger, 2017; Seifi et al., 2020; Uddin et al., 2022b, Uddin et al., 2022a).

5. Results and discussion

5.1. Statistical summary of selected water quality indicators

Indicator selection is the initial step in developing the WQI model. The present study selected eight water quality indicators, including DOX, MRP, DIN, TON, BOD₅, pH, TEMP, and TRAN, using the improved methodology of Uddin et al. (2022a). Details of the indicator concentration at each monitoring site can be found in Tables S2 to S9. Fig. S1 shows Pearson correlations among selected water quality indicators. There was a significant

negative correlation between nutrient enrichment indicators and other common indicators over the various domains through both the summer and winter seasons (Fig. S1). Fig. 4 shows a statistical summary of eight water quality indicators from various application domains over the course of the study. As shown in the figure below, a significant difference existed in the concentration level of various indicators between the summer and winter seasons across different waterbodies.

As regards Dublin Bay and Cork Harbour, most indicators were found between the guideline values, except the TON, TRAN, DIN, and MRP. These indicators exceeded the permissible limit during both the summer and winter seasons (Fig. 4a; Fig. 4b). In contrast to those domains, in Galway Bay, a slight data difference was found for water quality indicators throughout the year, whereas the majority of indicators were found within the permissible limit, with the exception of MRP for summer and DIN and MRP for winter, respectively, whereas those indicators breached the guide values for indicators in Galway Bay (Fig. 4c). Compared to other waterbodies, relatively, higher concentration differences were found between the summer and winter seasons in Mulroy Bay. The majority of indicators varied significantly throughout the year, but all indicators were found to be within the allowable limit during both seasons (Fig. 4d).

Fig. 5. SI values vs. indicator concentration at each monitoring sites in Dublin Bay over the summer season. Each black dot represent the SI value for each indicator at particular monitoring site.

Fig. 6. A statistical overview of the computed SI scores for selected eight water quality indicators across various waterbodies through the summer and winter season.

5.2. Sub-index results

In order to reduce the ambiguity problem in estimating SI values, the present study used three newly developed SI functions. Higher SI values typically denote “excellent” water quality, while lower values denote “poor” water quality. These SI functions were used in this research for computing the SI values due to their reliability and validity. Because these functions are effective in avoiding the eclipsing problem in computing SI values (Uddin et al., 2022a). Details of the SI functions and eclipsing can be found in Uddin et al. (2022a). Fig. 5 illustrates the sensitivity of aggregation functions using an example of a water quality indicator for Dublin Bay during the summer. Each black dot represents the SI value at a particular site for a given indicator concentration. The detailed SI values for each monitoring site across various water bodies during the study period are provided in Tables S11 to S18.

Fig. 6 presents a statistical summary of SI values for various application domains through the summer and winter periods. From the figure below, it can be seen that significant SI value differences were found between the summer and winter seasons across the application domains. Most indicators' SI values varied significantly through the year except for pH, TEMP, and TRAN (Fig. 6). Contrary to the waterbodies, BOD₅, and DOX significantly fluctuated over the study period, but relatively higher SI values were obtained for those indicators during the winter period in Dublin Bay (Fig. 6a).

Unlike Dublin Bay, a significant SI value difference was found between summer and winter periods for MRP and TON, whereas higher SI values were computed for those indicators in Cork Harbour over the summer season (Fig. 6b). Figs. 6c and 6d make it clear that SI values for the majority of water quality indicators in Galway Bay and Mulroy Bay varied seasonally. In both waterbodies, the majority of indicators' SI values were calculated between 75 and 100, with the exception of MRP in Mulroy Bay. The results of the SI values of various water quality indicators reveal that the SI functions are highly sensitive to the spatio-temporal resolution of the waterbodies.

5.3. Indicators weight values

The present study computed the indicator weight values using the improved methodology of Uddin et al. (2022a). Table 4 provides the weight

values for the eight indicators used to calculate the WQI scores. From the weight values in Table 4, nutrient indicators (TON, DIN, and MRP) achieved the highest weight values, whereas 0.222, 0.194, and 0.111, respectively, for TON, DIN, and MRP, had the most significant indicators in this research. Moreover, water TRAN and pH were also suggested as crucial indicators in terms of the physical attributes of coastal water quality. Contrarily, the water TEMP and DOX had the lowest significance when evaluating the quality of the coastal waters. The results of the weight values indicate that nutrient elements are more significant indicators for assessing coastal water quality than other indicators.

5.4. Results of the aggregation functions

The present study used the WQM aggregation function to transform the sub-indexes and weight values of selected indicators into the IEWQI score. The authors of a recent study have revealed that the WQM aggregation function is more effective and reliable compared to other functions in the existing system in terms of reducing model uncertainty. Details of this study can be found in Uddin et al. (2022a). The detailed results of the aggregation function at each monitoring site for four waterbodies during the summer and winter seasons can be found in Tables S2 to S9. Fig. 7 shows the summary statistics of WQI scores across various domains during the summer and winter, respectively. Fig. 8 presents the WQI scores at the

Table 4
Weight values of water quality indicators for the IEWQI model.

Indicators	Rank ^a	Weight values
TON	1	0.222
DIN	2	0.194
TRAN	3	0.167
pH	4	0.139
MRP	5	0.111
BOD ₅	6	0.083
TEMP	7	0.056
DOX	8	0.028
Sum		1.00

^a Indicators rank are assigned based on the relative importance obtained from the random forest technique.

Fig. 7. Statistical summary of IEWQI scores across the application domains in Ireland. The yellow circle indicates mean score; black line refers to the median score whereas the red circles designates the presence of data outliers.

monitoring site over the different waterbodies through the summer and winter seasons. From the figure (below), relatively higher WQI scores were found during the summer season, whereas scores were significantly lower during the winter season. As shown in Fig. 7, a significant difference was found in WQI scores between the summer and winter seasons for Cork Harbour. During both seasons, the data outlier's presence was found for Galway Bay and Mulroy Bay, whereas it was found only for Cork Harbour throughout the winter period. The results of the outliers indicate that the WQI scores had significant differences between the summer and winter seasons (Islam Khan et al., 2022; Uddin et al., 2022a).

For the determination of the relationship between IEWQI and inputs, the present study utilized the Pearson correlation analysis. Fig. S1 presents the Pearson correlation between various indicators and IEWQI scores. The correlation results indicate that most nutrient enrichment indicators have a strong negative correlation with the IEWQI scores, whereas water pH and TRAN show a strong positive correlation with IEWQI scores across four application domains during both seasons (Fig. S1).

5.4.1. Spatio-temporal differences of IEWQI scores

Figs. 9 and 10 present the spatiotemporal effects on aggregation function and variation of the calculated WQI score at each monitoring site across the various application domains, respectively. As shown in Fig. 8 (above), a slight difference in WQI scores was found between the summer and winter seasons for all waterbodies, with the exception of Cork Harbour. It can be seen from Figs. 8(b), 9(b), and 10(b), a significant WQI discrepancy was found between the summer and winter seasons in Cork Harbour. Relatively, lower WQI scores were estimated for the monitoring sites in the upper part of the Harbour (river Lee, north channel, and outer part of the Harbour), whereas higher WQI scores were calculated at the monitoring sites in the lower Harbour, river Owenacurra, and river Glashaboy (Fig. 9b) throughout the summer. Details of the monitoring sites' descriptions can be found in Table S1 and Fig. 1, respectively. The results of the spatio-temporal variation of WQI's in Cork indicate that the upper Harbour is sensitive in terms of receiving various pressures like anthropogenic, domestic wastewater, agricultural wastewater, etc. (Fig. S2; Fig. S3). In addition, the EPA Ireland also identified the upper part of the Harbour as a nutrient sensitive area (Environmental Protection Agency, 2021). The spatio-temporal results of the IEWQI scores in Cork Harbour are in line with those of previous studies (Environmental Protection Agency, 2021; News Releases, 2022; Uddin et al., 2020a, 2020b, 2022a, 2022b).

Like in Cork Harbour, relatively lower WQI scores were computed at the monitoring sites in the upper part of Dublin Bay, whereas higher scores were calculated from the farthest monitoring sites in the Bay during both the summer and winter seasons (Fig. 9a; Fig. 10a); because the

upper part has received a considerable amount of domestic wastewater (Environmental Protection Agency, 2021; Trodd and O'Boyle, 2019). It is noted that the EPA Ireland also noted the upper part of the Bay as a nutrient sensitive zone in previous reports (Barr and Mcelroy, 2019; Dublin Port Company, 2021). In contrast to the waterbodies, there were no significant differences in WQI scores for Galway Bay and Mulroy Bay throughout the study period (Fig. 9c; Fig. 9d; Fig. 10c; Fig. 10d). However, it can be easily figured out from the figure below that relatively higher WQI scores are computed at each monitoring site for most waterbodies through the winter period. The results of the spatio-temporal variation of WQI scores show that spatio-temporal resolution had a significant effect on the IEWQI model. As a result of the computed spatio-temporal differences in WQI scores, it is possible to conclude that the IEWQI model is highly sensitive to spatial attributes and that the model could compute the WQI score by taking the spatio-temporal resolution of waterbodies into account. Additionally, the IEWQI model could be integrated with the various anthropogenic and natural pressures present in the application domain and modelled as a result.

5.5. Impact of eclipsing and ambiguity attributes on the WQM aggregation function

A number of factors play a vital role in producing the uncertainty in the WQI model; the eclipsing and ambiguity are two of them. Details of the eclipsing and ambiguity attributes and their role in the WQI model can be found in Uddin et al. (2021) and Uddin et al. (2022a). Recently, several studies have revealed that these two attributes contribute a significant amount of uncertainty to the final assessment of water quality using the WQI model. In earlier studies, the authors have reported that the aggregation function is greatly influenced by these attributes. In their studies, Uddin et al. (2022a) proposed a few rules for determining the eclipsing and ambiguity impacts on the aggregation results. The present study determined the model eclipsing and ambiguity problems using the criteria and guidelines of Uddin et al. (2022a). The details of the eclipsing and ambiguity assessment criteria are discussed in Uddin et al. (2022a). Details of the model eclipsing results can be found in Tables S2 to S9. Herein, Table 5 provides a comprehensive statistical summary of model eclipsing and ambiguity problems that were obtained from the rule of Uddin et al. (2022a) across various application domains. Details of the eclipsing and ambiguity results are discussed below:

(i) Eclipsing results

The eclipsing problem commonly occurs due to over estimation of the WQI score by the aggregation function (Uddin et al., 2021, 2022a). Usually, it occurs when the aggregation function estimates more than the higher index score, or even if one or more indicators have breached the guideline

Fig. 8. Monitoring sites based IEWQI results across the four application domains in Ireland. The horizontal lines refer the IEWQI score to classify water quality using the classification scheme (see Table 3).

values, but the final index score does not reflect this circumstance (Uddin et al., 2022a). From the data in Table 5, it can be seen that the eclipsing problem can be found during summer season for most application domains with the exception of the Mulroy Bay, whereas it was found to be over the winter period. There were no eclipsing problems across various domains over the winter period except in Mulroy Bay. A number of monitoring sites were found to have the eclipsing problem across Dublin Bay (2 out of 24), Cork Harbour (5 out of 37), Galway Bay (1 out of 22) and Mulroy

Bay (3 out of 14), respectively (Table 5). Compared to the existing WQI models, the IEWQI model-eclipsing rate is lower than other techniques (Uddin et al., 2022a). The results of the eclipsing problem in the present study are consistent with those of the authors' earlier studies (Uddin et al., 2022a, 2022b).

(ii) Ambiguity results

Ambiguity is another crucial source of uncertainty in the WQI system that is associated with the sub-index and aggregation functions. It hides

Fig. 9. Spatio-temporal variation of the IEWQI scores are presented using the proportional symbol across various domains during the summer season.

the real information about water quality contained in the initial components of the model input. Commonly, it may be categorized into two, like *Type-I* and *Type-II*. Details of the ambiguity and its measurement criteria can be found in Uddin et al. (2022a). *Type-I* ambiguity relates to the underestimation problem of the aggregation function, whereas *Type-II* is associated with the overestimation problem of the aggregation method. The present study determined the ambiguity problem according to the approach of Uddin et al. (2022a). Because this method is particularly useful in studying the assessment of model ambiguity in the WQI technique, details of the model ambiguity results can be found in Tables S11 to S18. The present study found a *Type-II* ambiguity problem across different waterbodies in Ireland. Like the eclipsing problem, an ambiguity problem was found for Dublin Bay (4 out of 24 monitoring sites) and Cork Harbour (3 out of 37 monitoring sites) during the summer season, whereas there was no impact found over the winter period across most domains except for Mulroy Bay (1 out of 14 monitoring sites) (Table 5). During the study period, there was no ambiguity in Galway Bay. The ambiguity results show that the problem with ambiguity also affected the most eclipsed sites.

5.6. IEWQI prediction results

5.6.1. Model performance results

For the purposes of predicting the IEWQI score, the present study utilized the MLR technique. In order to evaluate the MLR performance, in this research, the 10-fold cross-validation technique was utilized because it is a widely used method in machine learning studies. Fig. 11 presents the various performance metrics of the MLR predictive model across various domains. Compared to the four domains, the lowest model prediction error (testing error) was found for Mulroy Bay (RMSE = 0.21, MSE = 0.045, MAE = 0.15 for summer, and RMSE = 0.36, MSE = 0.13, MAE = 0.32 for winter), and Galway Bay (RMSE = 0.23, MSE = 0.054, MAE = 0.19 for summer, and RMSE = 0.61, MSE = 0.38, MAE = 0.51 for winter), respectively during both seasons, whereas higher prediction errors were found for Dublin Bay (RMSE = 2.11, MSE = 4.45, MAE = 2.10 for summer, and RMSE = 1.72, MSE = 2.95, MAE = 1.45 for winter) and Cork Harbour (RMSE = 3.6, MSE = 12.96, MAE = 2.86 for summer, and RMSE = 3.69, MSE = 13.61, MAE = 3.63 for winter), respectively during model testing period (Fig. 11). Moreover, a higher prediction error was

Fig. 10. Spatio-temporal variation of the IEWQI scores are presented using the proportional symbol across various domains during the winter season.

found for those models during the training and testing periods. It can be seen from Fig. 11 that the model performance has improved significantly during the testing period across the four domains over the study period. Compared to the temporal resolution of the WQI model, the lowest prediction error was found for the summer season across the four application domains. The MLR model's results are in line with the author's earlier research, which showed that the model performed better for predicting IEWQI scores during the winter (Uddin et al., 2022a, 2022b).

5.6.2. Comparison of IEWQI prediction results

Fig. 12 shows the comparison results of WQI scores at each monitoring site across the four domains with a 95 % confidence interval and a significant level of $p < 0.001$. Fig. 7 (above) shows the summary statistics of actual and predicted WQI scores across various waterbodies over the study period. There was no significant difference between actual and predicted WQI scores during both seasons (Fig. 7). As can be seen from Fig. 12 below, in Dublin Bay, the MLR predicted the WQI score at each monitoring site

Table 5
The summary of statistics for the results of the IEWQI model eclipsing and ambiguity effects.

Attributes	Dublin Bay		Cork Harbour		Galway Bay		Mulroy Bay	
	Summer	Winter	Summer	Winter	Summer	Winter	Summer	Winter
Eclipsing	2 (8.3 %)	0	5 (13.5 %)	0	1 (4.5 %)	0	0	3 (21.4 %)
Ambiguity	4 (16.6 %)	0	3 (8.1 %)	0	0	0	0	1 (7.14 %)
Total sites	24	24	37	37	22	22	14	14

Fig. 11. Comparison of model performance in predicting the IEWQI scores for four application domains using various statistical measures.

accurately except for a single site during the summer season, whereas a relatively slight difference was found between the actual and predicted WQI score at most monitoring sites over the winter period (Fig. 12a). In contrast to other domains, a significant difference was found between the actual and predicted WQI score at most monitoring sites in Cork Harbour during both the summer and winter seasons (Fig. 12b). As shown in the data in the figure, compared to the uncertainty interval at each site, higher uncertainty was found for the Cork Harbour during the summer season than in the

winter period. During the summer, the MLR predicted WQI scores accurately at each monitoring site, whereas the model's prediction accuracy dropped during the winter period. Relatively, a slight difference was found between actual and predicted WQI scores, with a higher uncertainty interval during the winter period (Fig. 12c). On the other hand, in Mulroy Bay, from the data in Fig. 12d, the results indicate that there were no differences between actual and predicted WQI scores over both seasons (Fig. 12d). The prediction results revealed that the IEWQI model assessed

Fig. 12. Point based comparison between actual and predicted IEWQI scores over the application domains with a 95% confidence interval at $p < 0.05$, whereas the yellow shaded zone(s) indicates the uncertainty range of WQI scores.

Fig. 13. Relationship between actual and predicted IEWQI scores based on the testing datasets for four application domains over the summer season.

the water quality accurately in Mulroy Bay in terms of uncertainty. The results of the point assessment show that the uncertainty interval could be useful for figuring out how much uncertainty may be contributed by the IEWQI model across various domains in terms of spatiotemporal resolution. However, the present study has found a lower level of uncertainty (≤ 2) in the final assessment of water quality across various domains. Details of the uncertainty results can be found in Table 6 (below).

5.7. Model sensitivity results

For the purposes of sensitivity analysis of the IEWQI model in order to evaluate the model's performance in terms of spatiotemporal resolution of various application domains, the present study utilized the coefficient of determination (R^2). Recently, several water research studies have used this technique to assess the model's sensitivity (Chaudhary and Hantush, 2017; Uddin et al., 2022a, 2022b). Commonly, it allows one to determine

the relationship between model inputs (water quality indicators) and outputs (IEWQI score) using R^2 values. Its values range from 0 to 1, with higher values, which are typically close to 1, indicating the model's highest sensitivity to the input characteristics of the water quality of different domains. Figs. 13 and 14 present the R^2 score for the IEWQI model across four application domains, respectively, for the summer and winter seasons. Based on the R^2 score, with the exception of Cork Harbour, the highest sensitivity ($R^2 > 0.95$) was found for all domains during both seasons, whereas relatively the lowest R^2 was found for Cork Harbour during summer ($R^2 = 0.86$) and winter ($R^2 = 0.88$), respectively (Fig. 13b; Fig. 14b). The results of the R^2 values indicate that the IEWQI model is a good fit for assessing coastal water quality to any geospatial extent in Ireland with specific input attributes of water quality. Because in the majority of study cases, the IEWQI model can explain an average of 95 % of input entities, or the model converts all input attributes into the WQI score that presents the average of 95 % actual attributes of water quality indicators.

Fig. 14. Relationship between actual and predicted IEWQI scores based on the testing datasets for four application domains over the winter season.

5.8. Model uncertainty results

In order to evaluate the IEWQI model uncertainty in assessing the coastal water quality, the present study utilized the inferential error bar technique with a 95 % confidence interval, whereas the t-statistics were used for validation of the results of the error bar analysis. Table 6 provides the results of t-statistics for the IEWQI model over the different domains, whereas Fig. 15 presents the uncertainty results of the IEWQI model for various application domains (mean WQI values of actual and predicted, standard error, and 95 % confidence intervals of actual and MLR predicted IEWQI scores). The results of t-statistics indicate that there were no significant differences between actual and predicted IEWQI scores over the four application domains during both the summer and winter seasons. Moreover, the results of error bar analysis also reveal that there were no significant differences between actual and predicted WQI scores across various

application domains over the study period, with the exception of Cork Harbour and Dublin Bay.

As shown in the figure below, it can be seen clearly from the data that there was a slight difference in WQI score between actual and predicted scores during both seasons for both domains. Comparatively, the lowest standard error and standard deviation were found for Galway Bay and Mulroy Bay. The results of the uncertainty of the IEWQI model reflect the author's earlier studies (Uddin et al., 2022a, 2022c). However, the results of the t-statistics and error bar analysis indicate that the IEWQI model has no significant contribution to producing the uncertainty in the assessment of coastal water quality in terms of spatiotemporal resolution. Based on uncertainty results, the proposed WQI model could be effective for assessing coastal water quality more accurately, and it can be used in any spatial domain with a high level of statistical confidence in terms of reducing model uncertainty.

Table 6
t-statistics of IEWQI scores at $p < 0.000$ across various domains over the study period.

Temporal resolution	t-statistics	Dublin Bay (df = 23)		Cork Harbour (df = 36)		Galway Bay (df = 21)		Mulroy Bay (df = 13)	
		Actual	Predicted	Actual	Predicted	Actual	Predicted	Actual	Predicted
Summer	t-value	41.34	42.36	50.71	57.68	193.09	194.27	260.54	263.98
	mean	82.95	82.96	81.30	81.29	89.77	89.77	96.28	96.28
	SE	2.00	1.95	1.60	1.48	0.46	0.46	0.40	0.36
	SD	9.83	9.59	9.75	9.04	2.18	2.17	1.38	1.36
Winter	t-value	43.32	44.15	40.64	43.23	93.55	94.54	104.45	124.73
	mean	80.04	80.04	72.11	72.11	87.18	87.18	76.78	85.08
	SE	1.84	1.81	1.77	1.67	0.93	0.92	0.74	0.68
	SD	9.05	8.88	10.79	10.15	4.37	4.32	2.75	2.56

5.9. Model efficiency results

For the purposes of model efficiency analysis, the present study calculated the NSE and MEF using the actual and predicted IEWQI scores. Recently, a number of water research studies have utilized this tool to validate the model performance in terms of model efficiency (Guo et al., 2019; Izhar Shah et al., 2021; Jain and Sudheer, n.d.; Minh et al., 2022; Moriasi et al., 2015). Fig. 16 shows the site-specific NSE and MSE results for the IEWQI model across the various application domains. Table 7 provides summary statistics of NSE and MEF over the study period. The site-specific results of the model efficiency reveal that a slight variation was found across the various domains during both the summer and winter seasons. According to the NSE and MSE values, the IEWQI model shows better performance across various application domains, with the exception of Cork Harbour (Fig. 16) during both seasons. The model's efficiency was highest during the summer period when compared to its performance in terms of spatiotemporal resolution. In the case of each monitoring site assessment, the model performed efficiently at each monitoring site across the application domains, whereas at a few monitoring sites the model showed poor performance.

In Dublin Bay, over the study periods, the model performed more efficiently at each monitoring site during both seasons, with the exception of the DB420 site. The model shows poor performance ($NSE = -0.28$, and $MEF = 1.13$) at this point during the summer season. Relatively, higher NSE and MEF scores were calculated only for a few site-specific locations for the IEWQI model in Cork Harbour during both seasons. The results of NSE and MEF refer to the IEWQI model being over-fitted for predicting the WQI score in Cork Harbour. During both seasons, the models performed more efficiently at each monitoring site in both Galway Bay and Mulroy Bay, with the exception of the GY110 in Galway Bay and the MB050 in Mulroy Bay, respectively, during the winter period.

However, the results of NSE and MEF reveal that, for the assessment of site-specific water quality, the IEWQI model was performed efficiently across all application domains because the model can explain almost 95 % of the variance for the actual water quality indicators in terms of

their spatiotemporal resolution of various waterbodies. The results of the NSE of the present study are consistent with those of Guo et al. (2019), who also applied this technique for assessing the impact of key factors on the temporal variation of water quality models.

6. Assessment of water quality in Ireland

The ultimate goal of the IEWQI model is to assess and classify water quality using a specific classification scheme. For the classification of water quality, the present study used the improved classification scheme of Uddin et al. (2022a). Details of the classification are given in Table 3 above. Fig. 17 presents a summary of the water quality status across the four application domains in Ireland. Details of the assessment results for each monitoring site in all domains can be found in Table S2 to Table S9, respectively, for Dublin Bay, Cork Harbour, Galway Bay, and Mulroy Bay. Fig. S2 and Fig. S3 present the water quality status at each monitoring site in terms of spatio-temporal resolution of water quality in various application domains. Table S19 provides a comprehensive assessment of coastal and transitional water quality status over the various domains. The IEWQI model's results indicate that the two types of water quality dominated across the selected four domains through the study periods. From Fig. 17, it can be seen that water quality had "fair" and "good" classes across the domains during the summer and winter seasons.

There was a significant difference found between the summer and winter seasons in the water quality status across the domains. Relatively, most monitoring sites' water quality found "good" water quality during the summer season, whereas the quality degraded over the winter season across all domains (Fig. 17). The IEWQI results indicated that the majority of monitoring sites' water quality status was "fair" through the winter season.

Spatio-temporal variations of water quality and status at each monitoring site are presented in figs. S2 and S3, respectively, for the summer and winter seasons across the application domains. There was a significant variation in water quality between summer and winter seasons across the application domains. Details of the results of the spatio-temporal assessment

Fig. 15. Statistical significance of IEWQI model uncertainty for various application domains with 95 % confidence interval at <0.005 .

Fig. 16. Results of the IEWQI model efficiency at each monitoring site across the different application domain in Ireland in terms of spatiotemporal resolution.

can be found in Section 6.1 of the supplementary document as a continuation of Section 6.

However, the IEWQI model results reflect actual scenarios of water quality across application domains under different pressures in the existing domain settings. Moreover, the results of the present study are also in line with those of previous studies. The differences in water quality over the various domains between seasons may be due to the constituents of water

quality indicators in terms of various factors like the geospatial setting of the domains, different pressures on water bodies, etc.

7. Conclusion

An improved Irish Water Quality Index (IEWQI) model for assessing transitional and coastal waterbodies based on the legislation of Irish

Table 7
Summary statistics of the IEWQI model efficiency for assessing transitional and coastal water quality across the various domains in Ireland.

Application domains	Summer				Winter			
	NSE		MEF		NSE		MEF	
	Min.	Max.	Min.	Max.	Min.	Max.	Min.	Max.
(i) Dublin Bay	-0.28	1.00	0.00	1.13	0.00	0.99	0.00	1.00
(ii) Cork Harbour	-4.65	1.00	0.00	11.25	-4.83	17.90	0.00	2.41
(iii) Galway Bay	0.01	1.00	0.00	1.00	0.00	1.00	-0.78	0.92
(iv) Mulroy Bay	0.57	1.00	0.00	0.66	-3.87	1.52	0.00	1.51

Water Guidelines was proposed. The developed model was tested in four identical waterbodies in Ireland to evaluate model performance by comparing the spatio-temporal attributes of various application domains, and model performance was analysis using three advanced statistical measures, including the coefficient of determination for sensitivity, inferential error analysis for uncertainty, and NSE and MEF for efficiency analysis, respectively. The key findings from the research are as follows:

- (i) The sensitivity results of IEWQI indicate that the model outputs could be explained by >95 % of the input entities, including <2 % uncertainty with a 95 % confidence interval at $p < 0.0001$.
- (ii) The model performance validation results of NSE and MEF show that the IEWQI is superior for computing WQI scores at most monitoring sites across four application domains through the summer and winter periods.
- (iii) All statistical measures of performance metrics also indicate that the IEWQI model is more effective for the prediction of WQI, whereas the lowest prediction errors were found during the testing phase for predicting WQI scores across four waterbodies during summer and winter.
- (iv) The assessment results of water quality proved that the IEWQI model may be reliable for optimizing the model ambiguity and eclipsing problems.
- (v) Moreover, the performance of IEWQI applications reveals that suggested indicators might be adequate and reliable to monitor the transitional and coastal waters with the improved model.

Although the present study proposed the IEWQI model for transitional and coastal water quality, there is a high possibility that the IEWQI approach could be utilized to assess water quality in other waterbodies, particularly in rivers, lakes, and other bodies of water where saline water predominates. Despite the fact that the model was developed using water quality indicators for Cork Harbour, application results indicate that the IEWQI model could be used in any geospatial magnitude.

CRedit authorship contribution statement

- (1) **Md Galal Uddin:** Conceptualization, Methodology, Investigation, Formal analysis, ML and AI performed, Data curation, Visualization, Resources, Software, Writing – original draft, Writing – review & editing.
- (2) **Stephen Nash:** Conceptualization, Methodology, Investigation, Writing – review & editing.
- (3) **Azizur Rahaman:** Data curation, Methodology, Formal analysis, Conceptualization, Writing – review & editing.
- (4) **Agnieszka I. Olbert:** Conceptualization, Methodology, Investigation, Supervision, Data curation, Methodology, Writing – review & editing.

Data availability

No data was used for the research described in the article.

Declaration of competing interest

The authors confirm that they did not experience competing financial interests or personal interactions that could have had potential influences on this paper.

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Fig. 17. Statistical summary of water quality assessment results for four application domains over the study period.

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Appendix A. Supplementary data

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